

Testing the efficacy of two mycobacteriophage-antibiotic combinations against *Mycobacterium abscessus* biofilms

Carla Merchán Ruiz (s1127748)

Supervisors:

Dr. Jakko van Ingen (Jakko.vanIngen@radboudumc.nl)

Dr. Melissa McDaniel (melissa.mcdaniel@radboudumc.nl)

Department: Medical Microbiology, Radboud UMC Community for Infectious Diseases (Mycobacteria)

Master Internship: September 2024 – March 2025

** This Internship report is written following the guidelines for submission to ASM Journals (Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy) as a Short Research Paper*

ABSTRACT

Mycobacterium abscessus (MAB) is a highly drug-resistant pathogen capable of forming biofilms, which can reduce treatment efficacy. The aim of this study is to evaluate if combining bacteriophages and antibiotics enhances MAB eradication during biofilm formation compared to monotherapies. We tested two phages (Muddy and 8UZL) and two antibiotics (cefoxitin and tigecycline) against the clinical MAB strain GD01 under planktonic and biofilm conditions. The experimental conditions were optimized by confirming GD01 biofilm formation, selecting an appropriate growth medium, determining phage titers, establishing antibiotic minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values, and testing different multiplicity of infection (MOI) and antibiotic concentrations. Our results showed that phage-cefoxitin combinations were synergistic in planktonic cultures, but lost effectiveness in biofilms. Furthermore, tigecycline reduced phage titers in biofilms but not in planktonic cultures. These findings highlight the complexity of phage-antibiotic interactions in different bacterial growth states. Future directions include assessing phage and antibiotic resistance rates after treatment, determining phage penetration in biofilms with fluorescence microscopy, and investigating the molecular basis of cefoxitin synergy. Our study provides insights into optimizing phage-antibiotic strategies to improve therapeutic strategies for MAB infections.

INTRODUCTION

Mycobacterium abscessus (MAB) is an opportunistic pathogen that can cause severe lung infections in vulnerable populations, especially in people with cystic fibrosis (CF) and non-cystic fibrosis (non-CF) bronchiectasis (1). These chronic respiratory conditions are characterized by impaired mucociliary clearance and produce structural lung changes that facilitate the colonization of the lungs by environmental mycobacteria such as MAB. NTM are isolated in about 10% of bronchiectasis patients, and although the colonization does not always lead to disease, it can worsen inflammation and lung damage over time (2, 3).

Treating MAB infections is quite challenging due to its intrinsic antibiotic resistance, which comes from several factors including its impermeable cell wall, active efflux pumps, and its ability to form biofilms (4, 5). These biofilms are communities of bacteria encased in a self-produced extracellular matrix that can prevent antimicrobial penetration and contribute to persistent infections (4, 6). As a result, current treatment guidelines recommend prolonged combination therapies that involve multiple classes of antibiotics. Despite this intensive approach, the treatment success rates remain low, with a conversion rate between 33-45%, and significant toxicity (7–9).

Due to the limited success of conventional antibiotics, there is an increasing interest in alternative strategies, with the most promising being bacteriophage (phage) therapy or combined treatments (10, 11). Phages are viruses that specifically infect bacterial cells, with some capable of lysing their hosts. Clinical case reports have shown promising results using phage therapy to treat complex MAB infections, including those caused by rough colony morphotype strains such as GD01. These reports increased interest in developing new phage therapies, particularly in cases where antibiotics alone are insufficient. However, many questions remain, especially regarding how phages interact with antibiotics, particularly during a biofilm mode of growth.

Phages depend on active bacterial metabolism for their replication. This means that antibiotics that interfere with essential processes like transcription and translation could potentially reduce phage effectiveness. Many antibiotics commonly used against MAB, such as macrolides and aminoglycosides, inhibit protein synthesis, and could therefore interfere with phage replication processes. On the other hand, antibiotics with a different mechanism of action, such as β -lactams (cefoxitin) that target cell wall synthesis, might be considered more compatible. Understanding which antibiotics can be effectively combined with phages is crucial to develop effective therapeutic strategies.

Additionally, bacterial behavior in biofilms presents a particular challenge. Biofilms not only limit drug penetration but also contain slow-growing or metabolically inactive cells, which are less susceptible to both antibiotics and phages. Most of the successful phage applications have been described in planktonic conditions, where bacteria are more accessible. Whether similar results can be achieved in biofilms is still unclear, and remains a key question for optimizing phage therapy in clinical settings,

In this study, we evaluated the efficacy of two mycobacteriophages, Muddy and 8UZL, in combination with two antibiotics, cefoxitin (a β -lactam) and tigecycline (a protein synthesis inhibitor). We tested their activity against MAB strain GD01 in both planktonic and biofilm conditions. Our goal was to explore how these combinations influence bacterial clearance and phage amplification, and to determine whether phage-antibiotic synergy can be achieved under these conditions.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Bacterial strains and growth conditions

The clinical MAB strain GD01 was provided by Dr. Graham Hatfull (University of Pittsburgh, USA)'s laboratory. Bacterial cultures were grown in Middlebrook 7H9 broth supplemented with 10% oleic acid, albumin, dextrose and catalase (OADC) and 0.05% Tween 80 at 37°C with constant shaking (100 rpm). One week before starting the phage infection experiments, cultures were subcultured in Middlebrook 7H9 broth supplemented with 10% OADC and 1% calcium chloride (CaCl₂, 0.1M). Cation adjusted Mueller Hinton (CAMH) medium supplemented with CaCl₂ was used for all antibiotic and phage susceptibility assays.

Biofilm formation and planktonic cultures

Biofilms were generated following previously published methods(12, 13) with some modifications implemented. MAB GD01 was cultured in 96-well flat bottom microtiter plates using CAMH medium and incubated statically at 37°C for 96 hours with daily media changes to reach approximately 10⁶ CFU/mL. Planktonic cultures were grown under the same media conditions but overnight in shaking bottles at 37°C.

Bacteriophages

Two mycobacteriophages were used in this study: Muddy, donated by Dr. Graham Hatfull (University of Pittsburgh, USA), and 8UZL, provided by Dr. Jean-Paul Pirnay (Queen Astrid Military Hospital, Belgium). Phage stocks were prepared and stored in phage buffer (final concentrations are 10mM Tris, 10mM MgSO₄, 68mM NaCl, 1mM CaCl₂ and 10% glycerol). Phage propagation and amplification to increase phage titers was performed in liquid cultures of *Mycobacterium smegmatis* mc²155 grown in Middlebrook 7H9 broth supplemented with 10% OADC and 1% calcium chloride (CaCl₂, 0.1M), following the protocols described in the Phage Discovery Guide (<https://discoveryguide.seaphages.org/>).

Bacterial and phage quantification

For planktonic assays, 1mL samples were serially collected from the bottles at each time point. These were centrifuged at 8,800 rpm for 2 minutes. The supernatant was used to determine phage titers, while the pellet was resuspended and plated using a drip dilution method on Middlebrook 7H10 + OADC plates to quantify viable bacteria (14). To inactivate extracellular phages from the bacterial pellet, samples were treated with ferrous ammonium sulfate (FAS) before plating. Phage titers were quantified using spot tests based on the double agar layer method. Base plates were Middlebrook 7H10 agar supplemented with 1.25% glycerol, 0.2% dextrose and 1mM CaCl₂. The top layers were freshly prepared every sampling day and consisted of *Mycobacterium smegmatis* mc²155 culture with Middlebrook Top Agar (MBTA) and 7H9 broth supplemented with 1mM CaCl₂. Supernatants were serially diluted in phage buffer and dilutions were spotted on the overlay to determine plaque forming units (PFU).

For biofilm samples, the procedure detailed above was followed with some modifications. First, the biofilm supernatant was carefully collected without disturbing the bottom of the wells and was processed as described for planktonic supernatants to quantify phage titers. Then, FAS was added only to Muddy and 8UZL biofilms for 5 minutes. Subsequently, all biofilms were washed twice with PBS, scraped from the bottom of the wells, resuspended on 7H9 broth with Tween, and processed as described for planktonic pellet to quantify viable bacterial cells.

Antibiotics and susceptibility testing

Cefoxitin and tigecycline (Sigma-Aldrich) were prepared according to manufacturer instructions. Stock solutions were stored appropriately and diluted in sterile water for experiments. Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) were determined using the broth microdilution method following Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) M24 guidelines (15).

Time-kill kinetics

Susceptibility assays were performed in planktonic and biofilm conditions. Cultures were treated with phages and antibiotics alone and in combination. For biofilm assays, phages were applied at a multiplicity of infection (MOI) of 1:10 (bacteria:phage), while antibiotics were used at 1x and 4x MIC. For planktonic cultures, the MOI was 10:0.01 and the antibiotics were tested at 0.5x and 1x the MIC. Control wells were treated with either CAMH medium alone or FAS treated controls to rule out effects of phage carryover.

Statistical analysis

Statistical comparisons were performed using GraphPad Prism software (version 10.4.1). All experiments were performed in biological and technical triplicates. Area under the curve (AUC) analyses were performed to quantify overall treatment efficacy over time.

RESULTS

Phage monotherapy efficacy shows differences between planktonic and biofilm MAB GD01

Fig. 1 Differences in the efficacy of mycobacteriophages Muddy and 8UZL against MAB GD01 in planktonic and biofilm lifestyles. **(A) Planktonic cultures:** Left panel shows bacterial viability (CFU/mL) over time for untreated control (CAMH), phage inactivation control (FAS control), and cultures treated with phage Muddy and 8UZL at MOI 1:10. Right panel corresponds to phage titers (PFU/mL) over the same time. **(B) Biofilm cultures:** Left panel shows bacterial survival in preestablished biofilms treated under the same conditions. Right panel corresponds to phage titers in biofilm cultures. Data points represent means from three independent experiments with three technical replicates. LOD = limit of detection ($2\log_{10}$ CFU/mL for bacteria, $2\log_{10}$ PFU/mL for phages).

We first compared the ability of the two mycobacteriophages Muddy and 8UZL, to reduce bacterial viability in both planktonic and biofilm lifestyles of MAB GD01. Planktonic cultures were inoculated in liquid medium and biofilms were grown and matured prior to adding the treatment.

Both phages showed a strong lytic activity against planktonic MAB GD01 resulting in a fast and significant bacterial load decrease (Fig. 1A). The bacteriophage Muddy decreased the amount of viable bacteria from 10^3 CFU/mL to a count close to the limit of detection (LOD) within 4 days. Similarly, the 8UZL phage achieved similar bacterial clearance, with almost complete elimination by day 5 (Fig. 1A).

Phage titers showed characteristic amplification patterns in planktonic cultures (Fig. 1A, right panel). Both phages rapidly increased from 10^6 to 10^9 PFU/mL during the initial 2-3 days, which corresponds with the time of maximal bacterial killing. Phage titers then stabilized at elevated levels for the rest of the sampling period (Fig. 1B).

In contrast to planktonic results, when applied to biofilms, neither phage significantly reduced the amount of viable MAB GD01 (Fig. 1B). Despite using the same MOI conditions as in planktonic experiments, bacterial counts remained relatively stable during the 5 days of observation, only showing

minimal reduction compared to untreated controls (Fig. 1B, left panel). Despite the apparent absence of bacterial killing in biofilms, phage titers showed a continuous increase throughout the experiment and also plateaued at day 3 (Fig. 1B, right panel).

Synergistic effects of phage-cefoxitin combinations

Fig. 2 Synergistic effects of mycobacteriophage-cefoxitin combinations in planktonic and biofilm cultures of MAB GD01. (A-B) planktonic cultures: Time-kill kinetics of bacterial viability (left panels) and area under the curve (AUC) quantification (right panels) for MAB GD01 treated with Muddy (A) or 8UZL (B) phages alone, cefoxitin (FOX) at 8 and 16 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (0.5x and 1x MIC, respectively) or phage-antibiotic combinations. **(C-D) Biofilm cultures:** Time-kill analysis for 96h old biofilms treated with

Muddy (C) or 8UZL (D) phages and FOX at 16 and 64 µg/mL (which corresponds to 1x and 4x MIC). Growth control represents untreated bacteria. Data points represent means from three independent experiments with three replicates each.

Following the limited efficacy of phage treatment on biofilms, we then tested the efficacy of phage and antibiotic combinations on MAB killing. For these results, planktonic and biofilm cultures of MAB GD01 were treated with either phage alone, antibiotic alone or their combinations. MIC determinations indicated susceptibility to ceftiofur and tigecycline and optimization experiments showed that CAMH was an appropriate medium for both biofilm formation and antibiotic stability, as it showed similar or slightly higher growth compared to 7H9 under both conditions (Fig. S1, Table S2).

In planktonic cultures of MAB GD01, the combination of both phages with ceftiofur showed clear synergistic impact (Fig. 2A-B). Muddy combined with ceftiofur at both tested concentrations (8 and 16 µg/mL) improved bacterial reduction compared to each treatment alone. The strongest effect was observed in the combination of Muddy and ceftiofur 16 µg/mL, with a decrease in bacterial counts of 3.2 log₁₀ CFU/mL by day 8, which represents more than 2 log₁₀ improvement over phage monotherapy (Fig. 2A). Similar results were seen with 8UZL and ceftiofur at a concentration of 16 µg/mL, with a bacterial decrease of 3 log₁₀ CFU/mL (Fig. 2B). AUC analyses confirmed that the combination treatments led to improved bacterial clearance, as they showed lower AUC values when compared to individual therapies.

Despite these clear synergistic effects, this therapeutic benefit was completely lost when the same combinations were tested against MAB GD01 biofilms (Fig. 2C-D). Both Muddy-ceftiofur and 8UZL-ceftiofur combinations were not more effective than the individual treatments, and bacterial counts remained stable during the treatment period regardless of antibiotic concentration.

Tigecycline negatively affects bacterial clearance during combination treatment

Fig. 3 Tigecycline and phage combinations show antagonistic interactions in biofilm environments. (A-B) Planktonic cultures: Time-kill kinetics of bacterial viability (left panels) and area under the curve (AUC) quantification (right panels) for

MAB GD01 treated with Muddy (A) or 8UZL (B) phages alone, tigecycline (TGC) at 0.25 and 0.5 µg/mL (0.5x and 1x MIC, respectively) or phage-antibiotic combinations. (C-D) Biofilm cultures: Time-kill analysis for 96h old biofilms treated with Muddy (C) or 8UZL (D) phages and TGC at 0.5 and 2 µg/mL (which corresponds to 1x and 4x MIC). Growth control represents untreated bacteria. Data points represent means from three independent experiments with three replicates each.

We then explored the interaction between the tigecycline and the two phages in both planktonic and biofilm MAB GD01 cultures. The combination of both mycobacteriophages with tigecycline revealed different interaction patterns than those in cefoxitin combinations (Fig. 3).

In planktonic cultures, tigecycline monotherapy had a relatively low antimicrobial effect against MAB GD01 with bacterial counts remaining stable between 5 and 6 log₁₀ CFU/mL even with higher antibiotic concentrations. When we combined with either Muddy or 8UZL phages, the resulting bacterial clearance patterns were nearly identical to phage monotherapy (Fig. 3A-B).

In biofilm cultures, phage tigecycline interactions revealed a more complex pattern. The antibiotic showed moderate activity against biofilms by lowering the bacterial counts by approximately 1 log₁₀ CFU/mL. However, combination treatments did not improve bacterial clearance compared to individual approaches (Fig. 3C-D).

This antagonism was especially obvious in both phage-tigecycline combinations, where the bacterial decrease was comparable or even less than the antibiotic alone.

The impact of antibiotics on phage viability varies between antibiotic classes and bacterial lifestyle

Fig. 4 Antibiotic classes affect phage viability on a different way. (A) Muddy phage titer dynamics: Phage viability (PFU/mL) over time in planktonic cultures (left panel, 0-10 days) and biofilm cultures (right panel, 0-5 days) when combined with ceftioxin (FOX) at a low MIC (8 µg/mL planktonic, 16 µg/mL biofilms) and high MIC (16 µg/mL planktonic and 64 µg/mL biofilm) or tigecycline (TGC) at low MIC (0.25 µg/mL planktonic, 0.5 µg/mL biofilms) and high MIC (0.5 µg/mL planktonic and 2 µg/mL biofilm). **(B) 8UZL phage titer dynamics:** Phage viability analysis for 8UZL under the same treatment conditions. Controls are Muddy and 8UZL phage monotherapy alone. Data points represent means from three independent experiments with three replicates each.

To investigate why treatment synergism was not seen with tigecycline, we measured phage viability (PFU/mL) over time with exposure to ceftioxin or tigecycline at different concentrations, both in planktonic and also in biofilm settings. Muddy and 8UZL phages were tested under the same MOI and conditions and both antibiotics were applied at low and high MICs depending on each growth mode.

In planktonic cultures neither ceftioxin nor tigecycline had significant effect on Muddy or 8UZL phage titers. Both phages were able to replicate in the presence of antibiotics reaching and maintaining titers of 10^{10} PFU/mL throughout the 10 days of sampling period (Fig. 4A-B, left panels).

In contrast, there is a great difference with the results of biofilm conditions. While ceftioxin had minimal impact on phage titers in biofilms, the presence of tigecycline caused a concentration dependent decrease in the viability of both phages. This reduction was evident from day 1 and persisted throughout the experiment. A decrease of approximately $4\log_{10}$, was observed with the low concentration of tigecycline, whereas a $6\log_{10}$ decrease happened to both phages when they were applied together with high tigecycline concentrations in biofilm environments (Fig 4A-B, right panels).

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the efficacy of two mycobacteriophage-antibiotic combinations against MAB, revealing important differences in the treatment outcomes between planktonic and biofilm growth conditions. The main goal was to assess if phage-antibiotic combinations can improve the bactericidal activity of each other when applied together, especially in biofilm state which is clinically relevant for patients with chronic MAB infections. Our findings showed that while phage therapy shows promising results in planktonic conditions, particularly in combination with certain antibiotics, the biofilm environment presents challenges that may limit the efficacy of the treatment.

One of the key findings of this study is that both Muddy and 8UZL phages were effective against planktonic MAB GD01 cultures, but not against biofilms. These results align with the expected behavior of phages in planktonic conditions, where bacteria are freely accessible to phage and there are no physical barriers preventing phage contact. This is also consistent with previous reports of successful phage therapy against MAB in clinical settings (16). However, no phage achieved complete bacterial elimination, and the remaining bacterial populations persisted near the detection limit throughout the observation period. This may be attributed to phenotypic heterogeneity or intrinsic resistance.

In contrast, in biofilm conditions, phage treatment alone did not lead to noticeable bacterial reduction, despite evidence of phage amplification. Biofilms provide protection to the bacteria via several mechanisms. First, the extracellular polymeric substance matrix characteristic of biofilms physically interferes with phage penetration, preventing direct contact between phages and embedded bacteria (4). MAB biofilms are particularly challenging in patients with cystic fibrosis, where they create strong extracellular matrices made mainly of extracellular DNA, glycans that include glucose and mannose and phospholipids (17). MAB pathogenicity is linked to the ability to form biofilms where the extracellular matrix acts as a physical barrier that prevents drug penetration and protects bacteria from the immune system. This physical barrier is considered a limitation for antimicrobial penetration in biofilm-associated infections (18). Second, biofilm bacteria exhibit different metabolic states, such as slow growth rates, non-replicative state and different gene expression patterns, making them less susceptible to phage infection that relies on host machinery for genome replication, protein synthesis and phage assembly (17). Previous studies have shown that MAB biofilms have increased levels of antibiotic tolerance compared to planktonic cultures, especially when grown under conditions that mimic cystic fibrosis infections (19, 20).

Interestingly, despite the lack of bacterial killing, phage amplification was observed in biofilm conditions. This may indicate that phages were able to use the host machinery for their replication in more permissive areas such as the outer layers of the biofilm, where the bacterial metabolism is still active. This observation provides evidence for the existence of an equilibrium between biofilm dispersal and phage killing. It is possible that this phage amplification in the absence of killing is due to phage replication in the dispersed outer layer of the biofilm, while the inner layers remain protected. This complex behavior can be a result of biofilm microenvironments and may result in increased phage counts which are not reflected in an overall bacterial reduction.

The synergistic interaction observed between cefoxitin and both phages in planktonic conditions represents a key finding with potential clinical implications, as it suggests that cefoxitin not only allows for phage replication but may also actively enhance phage mediated bacterial killing in planktonic conditions. The mechanism underlying this synergy might involve cefoxitin's mechanism of action. As a β -lactam it is involved in the disruption of peptidoglycan synthesis, which could weaken bacterial cell walls and facilitate phage infection or enhance the efficiency of lysis mediated by phages. This finding aligns with previous studies that β -lactam antibiotics may improve phage therapy efficacy against

Pseudomonas aeruginosa. In this case, the bacterial cell wall was weakened due to the use of β -lactams and it increased bacterial susceptibility to phage infection (21). In our experiments this synergy seemed to be dose-dependent, as the higher cefoxitin concentrations produced better enhancement. However, this synergistic effect was completely lost under biofilm conditions; cefoxitin did not seem to inhibit phage replication but there was no bacterial clearance.

On the other hand, when tigecycline was combined with the phages in planktonic conditions, the bacterial clearance patterns were nearly identical to phage monotherapy. This suggests that the killing effect was primarily driven by phage activity rather than any synergistic interactions. Moreover, the antagonistic effect of tigecycline on phage therapy, particularly in biofilm conditions, is a concerning finding. Tigecycline functions as a protein synthesis inhibitor and binds to the 30S ribosomal subunit to block aminoacyl-tRNA binding, directly affecting the bacterial translational machinery required for phage reproduction (22). In biofilm conditions, where bacterial metabolism is reduced and cellular resources are limited, this interference becomes particularly crucial for phage mediated bacterial killing. Although studies have shown that tigecycline exhibits potent activity against MAB, our observations indicate that this activity is not present when combined with phages in biofilm conditions (23). The fact that tigecycline specifically compromises the phage viability in biofilm conditions suggests that protein synthesis inhibitors may be contraindicated in phage combination therapies targeting biofilm infections. To our knowledge, this is the first study to demonstrate this antagonistic interaction between phages and protein synthesis inhibitors in MAB. This finding is consistent with previous reports in other pathogens, where these interactions are further exacerbated in biofilm environments where bacterial metabolism is already compromised (24).

Interestingly, a recent study reported a successful synergistic combination of tigecycline and phages against 5 different *Acinetobacter baumannii* strains in planktonic conditions and also increasing phage titers (25). This contrast with our findings in MAB GD01 biofilms may be explained by the different bacterial lifestyles. In our model, the combination is applied to preformed biofilms of MAB GD01 where metabolic activity is lower than free-living cells. Therefore, it is possible that the few metabolically active cells are rapidly targeted and killed by tigecycline before phages have a chance to replicate inside them. As a result, this would lead to a reduction in viral load, as observed in our experiments.

This difference in phage efficacy between planktonic and biofilm states highlights the challenge of treating biofilm-associated NTM infections with phage therapy alone. It is also important to note that both phages used for the experiments are closely related, possibly explaining their similar performance in assays. The persistence of phage titers in planktonic cultures suggests that both classes, despite their different modes of action, do not inhibit phage propagation when the bacterial metabolism is active and there are abundant resources. This together supports the potential combination therapy on this setting.

Before addressing the limitations of our study, it is also important to mention that all the experiments were performed using a MAB clinical strain that shows rough colony morphotype. MAB is known to exist in two different morphotypes: smooth and rough (26). The main difference between these two forms is in the composition of their cell surface. Smooth morphotypes produce glycopeptidolipids (GLPs) that create shiny, slimy and non-cording colonies, whereas the rough morphotypes lack these GLPs and the colonies are matte, with irregular shapes and often create cords when observed microscopically. Rough strains are associated with an increased virulence and are more likely to cause severe and persistent infections, as the presence of GLPs is associated with less virulence (27). Relevant for our study is that recent research has shown that the rough morphotype is more susceptible to bacteriophage infection and killing than the smooth morphotype (28). This difference in susceptibility is associated with the absence of GLPs in rough strains; this exposes the bacterial surface receptors and makes phage attachment and entry easier. In contrast, the surface of smooth strains is rich on GLPs acting as a barrier

against phage attachment. The choice of a rough morphotype for this project is highly relevant to patient outcomes, but these findings may not directly translate to infections caused by smooth morphotype strains.

Several limitations should be acknowledged while interpreting these results. First, cefoxitin is not typically used for MAB treatment, which limits the direct clinical applicability of the observed synergy. However, it was useful as an effective model β -lactam antibiotic to show the principle of phage-antibiotic synergy. Recent studies have promising results for dual β -lactam combinations, specially meropenem with ceftazidime-avibactam, which show synergistic effects with phages and were successful in treating MAB infections (29).

Moreover, tigecycline's light sensitivity and instability showed some technical challenges during the study, potentially affecting the consistency of results. Future research should explore alternative antibiotic classes for combination with phage therapy, particularly those that previously show anti-biofilm activity. Electron transport chain inhibitors like clofazimine could be promising candidates for future studies and should be tested for compatibility with phages.

Further research could include investigation into strategies that enhance phage penetration into biofilms or disrupt biofilm structure prior to phage administration, which could improve therapeutic outcomes. Another approach could be the development of engineered phages with enhanced capacity to penetrate or degrade biofilms, or the use of phage cocktails with complementary activities. These approaches focus on disrupting the biofilm structure and increasing bacterial susceptibility to antimicrobial agents and could potentially restore the synergistic effects observed in planktonic conditions.

CONCLUSION

This study shows that while phage-antibiotic combinations show promise for treating MAB infections, their efficacy is strongly influenced by bacterial growth conditions and antibiotic selection. The lack of synergistic effects in biofilm conditions and the antagonistic effects of some antibiotics highlight the complexity of developing effective phage therapy protocols. These findings highlight the need to carefully consider the growth conditions and the antibiotic compatibility in the design of future phage therapy regimens for MAB infections.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to thank my daily supervisor, Melissa McDaniel, for being such a supportive and dedicated mentor during this internship. Always attentive and willing to help with anything, both inside and outside the lab, she played a key role in my personal and professional growth. I have learned a lot from her, not only about science and research, but also about scientific reasoning and critical thinking. Her guidance has been very important for my development as a young researcher.

I am especially grateful to Dr. Jakko van Ingen for giving me this opportunity, welcoming me from the very beginning, and saying yes to my ambitious project proposal without hesitation. His feedback during our regular weekly meetings helped me improve my project and approach my experiments from different perspectives, always encouraging me to ask questions and think critically, a mindset that I am sure will be essential in my future career.

I am particularly thankful to someone who, while not officially my supervisor, certainly felt like one, Marta Pozuelo Torres. From the start, she made my daily lab routine much more enjoyable and manageable. She was always ready to answer my questions, and most importantly, she always made sure I truly understood the procedures involved. Her knowledge was essential for the success of my project, and the same applies to Saskia Janssen, whose assistance and valuable input I also really appreciate.

A special mention goes to Eva Terschlüsen, who has always been a great support for everyone in the lab. Despite her heavy workload and administrative responsibilities, she consistently made sure everything ran smoothly, and that people felt supported.

Finally, I want to thank all the lab members, from the diagnostics technicians to the research team, for their warm welcome and daily support. Being part of this group over the past seven months has been an enriching experience, and I will always be grateful that they made me feel like part of their family.

REFERENCES

1. Esther CR, Esserman DA, Gilligan P, Kerr A, Noone PG. 2010. Chronic Mycobacterium abscessus infection and lung function decline in cystic fibrosis. *J Cyst Fibros* 9:10.1016/j.jcf.2009.12.001.
2. Zhou Y, Mu W, Zhang J, Wen SW, Pakhale S. 2022. Global prevalence of non-tuberculous mycobacteria in adults with non-cystic fibrosis bronchiectasis 2006–2021: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ Open* 12:e055672.
3. Bonaiti G, Pesci A, Marruchella A, Lapadula G, Gori A, Aliberti S. 2015. Nontuberculous Mycobacteria in Noncystic Fibrosis Bronchiectasis. *Biomed Res Int* 2015:197950.
4. Dokic A, Peterson E, Arrieta-Ortiz ML, Pan M, Di Maio A, Baliga N, Bhatt A. 2021. Mycobacterium abscessus biofilms produce an extracellular matrix and have a distinct mycolic acid profile. *Cell Surf* 7:100051.
5. Ju Y, Li L, Zhang J, Yusuf B, Zeng S, Fang C, Tian X, Han X, Ding J, Zhang H, Ma W, Wang S, Chen X, Zhang T. 2024. The gene MAB_2362 is responsible for intrinsic resistance to various drugs and virulence in Mycobacterium abscessus by regulating cell division. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* 69:e00433-24.
6. Gloag ES, Wozniak DJ, Stoodley P, Hall-Stoodley L. 2021. Mycobacterium abscessus biofilms have viscoelastic properties which may contribute to their recalcitrance in chronic pulmonary infections. *Sci Rep* 11:5020.
7. Degiacomi G, Sammartino JC, Chiarelli LR, Riabova O, Makarov V, Pasca MR. 2019. Mycobacterium abscessus, an Emerging and Worrisome Pathogen among Cystic Fibrosis Patients. *Int J Mol Sci* 20:5868.
8. Dorn A van. 2017. Multidrug-resistant Mycobacterium abscessus threatens patients with cystic fibrosis. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine* 5:15.
9. Floto RA, Olivier KN, Saiman L, Daley CL, Herrmann J-L, Nick JA, Noone PG, Bilton D, Corris P, Gibson RL, Hempstead SE, Koetz K, Sabadosa KA, Sermet-Gaudelus I, Smyth AR, van Ingen J, Wallace RJ, Winthrop KL, Marshall BC, Haworth CS. 2016. US Cystic Fibrosis Foundation and European Cystic Fibrosis Society consensus recommendations for the management of non-tuberculous mycobacteria in individuals with cystic fibrosis. *Thorax* 71:i1–i22.
10. Johansen MD, Alcaraz M, Dedrick RM, Roquet-Banères F, Hamela C, Hatfull GF, Kremer L. 2021. Mycobacteriophage–antibiotic therapy promotes enhanced clearance of drug-resistant Mycobacterium abscessus. *Dis Model Mech* 14:dmm049159.
11. Hatfull GF. 2018. Mycobacteriophages. *Microbiol Spectr* 6.
12. O’Toole GA. 2011. Microtiter dish biofilm formation assay. *J Vis Exp* 2437.

13. McDaniel MS, Edmonds SE, Patel EN, Baty JJ, Scoffield JA. 2025. Mycobacterium abscessus promotes Pseudomonas aeruginosa biofilm formation and antibiotic tolerance. bioRxiv <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.12.31.630905>.
14. Jett BD, Hatter KL, Huycke MM, Gilmore MS. 1997. Simplified Agar Plate Method for Quantifying Viable Bacteria. *BioTechniques* 23:648–650.
15. Brown-Elliott BA, Woods GL. 2019. Antimycobacterial Susceptibility Testing of Nontuberculous Mycobacteria. *J Clin Microbiol* 57:e00834-19.
16. Hashemi Shahraki A, Mirsaiedi M. 2021. Phage Therapy for Mycobacterium Abscessus and Strategies to Improve Outcomes. *Microorganisms* 9:596.
17. Belardinelli JM, Li W, Avanzi C, Angala SK, Lian E, Wiersma CJ, Palčeková Z, Martin KH, Angala B, de Moura VCN, Kerns C, Jones V, Gonzalez-Juarrero M, Davidson RM, Nick JA, Borlee BR, Jackson M. 2021. Unique Features of Mycobacterium abscessus Biofilms Formed in Synthetic Cystic Fibrosis Medium. *Front Microbiol* 12.
18. Lira RL de S, Nogueira FAB, Campos R de FP de C, Ferreira DRM, Roxo PLBT, de Azevedo CCS, Gimenes ECM, Bastos RLC, Nascimento CEC, Nunes FDO, Marques MCP, Campos CDL, Martinez CG, Zagmignan A, Silva LCN, Ribeiro RM, de Azevedo dos Santos APS, Carvalho RC, de Sousa EM. 2025. Mycobacterium abscessus subsp. massiliense: Biofilm Formation, Host Immune Response, and Therapeutic Strategies. 2. *Microorganisms* 13:447.
19. Keefe BF, Bermudez LE. 2022. Environment in the lung of cystic fibrosis patients stimulates the expression of biofilm phenotype in Mycobacterium abscessus. *Journal of Medical Microbiology* 71:001467.
20. Hunt AC, Boll J, Boutte C. 2018. Biofilm-associated Mycobacterium abscessus cells have altered antibiotic tolerance and surface glycolipids in Artificial Cystic Fibrosis Sputum Media. bioRxiv <https://doi.org/10.1101/479923>.
21. Holger DJ, El Ghali A, Bhutani N, Lev KL, Stamper K, Kebriaei R, Kunz Coyne AJ, Morrisette T, Shah R, Alexander J, Lehman SM, Rojas LJ, Marshall SH, Bonomo RA, Rybak MJ. 2023. Phage-antibiotic combinations against multidrug-resistant Pseudomonas aeruginosa in in vitro static and dynamic biofilm models. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* 67:e00578-23.
22. Schildkraut JA, Coolen JPM, Burbaud S, Sangen JN, Kwint MP, Floto RA, op den Camp HJM, te Brake LHM, Wertheim HFL, Neveling K, Hoefsloot W, van Ingen J. RNA Sequencing Elucidates Drug-Specific Mechanisms of Antibiotic Tolerance and Resistance in Mycobacterium abscessus. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 66:e01509-21.
23. Pearce C, Ruth MM, Pennings LJ, Wertheim HFL, Walz A, Hoefsloot W, Ruesen C, Muñoz Gutiérrez J, Gonzalez-Juarrero M, van Ingen J. 2020. Inhaled tigecycline is effective against Mycobacterium abscessus in vitro and in vivo. *J Antimicrob Chemother* 75:1889–1894.

24. Kunz Coyne AJ, Eshaya M, Bleick C, Vader S, Biswas B, Wilson M, Deschenes MV, Alexander J, Lehman SM, Rybak MJ. Exploring synergistic and antagonistic interactions in phage-antibiotic combinations against ESKAPE pathogens. *Microbiol Spectr* 12:e00427-24.
25. Choi Y-J, Kim S, Shin M, Kim J. 2024. Synergistic Antimicrobial Effects of Phage vB_AbaSi_W9 and Antibiotics against *Acinetobacter baumannii* Infection. *Antibiotics (Basel)* 13:680.
26. Rüger K, Hampel A, Billig S, Rücker N, Suerbaum S, Bange F-C. 2014. Characterization of Rough and Smooth Morphotypes of *Mycobacterium abscessus* Isolates from Clinical Specimens. *J Clin Microbiol* 52:244–250.
27. Hedin W, Fröberg G, Fredman K, Chryssanthou E, Selmerud I, Gillman A, Orsini L, Runold M, Jönsson B, Schön T, Davies Forsman L. 2023. A Rough Colony Morphology of *Mycobacterium abscessus* Is Associated With Cavitory Pulmonary Disease and Poor Clinical Outcome. *The Journal of Infectious Diseases* 227:820–827.
28. Dedrick RM, Smith BE, Garlena RA, Russell DA, Aull HG, Mahalingam V, Divens AM, Guerrero-Bustamante CA, Zack KM, Abad L, Gauthier CH, Jacobs-Sera D, Hatfull GF. 2021. *Mycobacterium abscessus* Strain Morphotype Determines Phage Susceptibility, the Repertoire of Therapeutically Useful Phages, and Phage Resistance. *mBio* 12:e03431-20.
29. Cristinziano M, Shashkina E, Chen L, Xiao J, Miller MB, Doligalski C, Coakley R, Lobo LJ, Footer B, Bartelt L, Abad L, Russell DA, Garlena R, Lauer MJ, Viland M, Kaganovsky A, Mowry E, Jacobs-Sera D, van Duin D, Kreiswirth BN, Hatfull GF, Friedland A. 2024. Use of epigenetically modified bacteriophage and dual beta-lactams to treat a *Mycobacterium abscessus* sternal wound infection. *Nat Commun* 15:10360.
30. Senhaji-Kacha A, Esteban J, Garcia-Quintanilla M. 2020. Considerations for Phage Therapy Against *Mycobacterium abscessus*. *Front Microbiol* 11:609017.

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Fig. S1. Assessment of CAMH and 7H9 media on MAB GD01 growth in planktonic and biofilm conditions. The left panel shows the \log_{10} CFU/mL of planktonic cultures measured at 24, 48, 72, 96 and 120 hours. The right panel shows the \log_{10} CFU/mL of biofilm cultures at the same timepoints. Results is represented with blue squares for CAMH (cation-adjusted Mueller-Hinton broth) and purple circles for 7H9. LOD (limit of detection) = $2\log_{10}$ CFU/mL MAB GD01

Strain	MIC ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)											
	IPM	FOX	CLR	TGC	CFZ	AMK	CIP	LNZ	DOX	TOB	MXF	SXT
MAB GD01	32	16	>16	0.5	0.12	>256	>4	16	>8	>16	>4	>4/76

Table S1. Drug susceptibility/resistance profile of MAB GD01. MIC were determined at day 4 of incubation, following the CLS guidelines. The numbers under the antibiotic abbreviations show the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) in $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Imipenem (IMP), ceftazidime (CFZ), clarithromycin (CLR), tigecycline (TGC), clofazimine (CFZ), amikacin (AMK), ciprofloxacin (CIP), linezolid (LNZ), doxycycline (DOX), tobramycin (TOB), moxifloxacin (MXF), and trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole (SXT).